

Optimization of battery/supercapacitor-based PV household-prosumers providing self-consumption and frequency containment reserve as influenced by temporal data granularity

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Abstract

Service complementarity between a frequency containment reserve and PV self-consumption can increase incomes for household-prosumers. Moreover, battery/supercapacitor-based hybrid energy storage systems (HESSs) play a major role. Fitting power and energy management improve HESS performance, and therefore increase the profitability of the asset. Furthermore, component sizing is critical. To achieve both targets, we developed a hybrid meta-heuristic optimization algorithm that deals with the management strategies and sizing. Accordingly, a four-dimensional, non-linear, non-convex, and mixed-integer optimization problem was formulated, and a cost function was minimized by combining the Haar wavelet (WT) transform and the teaching-learning-based optimization (TLBO) method. The algorithm has a flexible design, which is adapted in terms of a number of discrete states to suit input profiles defined according to different time discretizations. The effectiveness of the algorithm was proved by using different data granularity for a PV prosumer in Spain in various service scenarios. The simulations performed in this study reflected both technical and economic impacts. The results suggest that for optimization purposes, high-resolution data should be used to consider the full range of input fluctuations. However, these results largely depend on the service scenario setup. Indeed, in some scenarios, accurate results were obtained by using coarse-grained data, which entailed a lower computational burden. In contrast, in other scenarios, it was preferable to use data with a higher resolution. The optimal combination of services significantly increased the profitability of the asset.

Keyword: PV power; frequency containment reserve; lifetime; hybrid energy storage system; multi-objective optimization; temporal data granularity.

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Nomenclature. List of symbols

Symbol	Description
ψ	Mother wavelet function
$\Delta_t = t_f / N_t$	Discretization time-step (sampling interval) [0.5 – 30 min]
$\Delta_s e_{fcr,k}$ ($\Delta_t e_{fcr,k}$)	Cumulated shortage(surplus) FCR energy supply vis-à-vis their nomination in the PV household-prosumer
$[\Delta_s E_{fcr,k}$ ($\Delta_t E_{fcr,k}$)]	[MFCRU] at any period k [kWh]
ε_{bt}	MBU self-discharge coefficient [%/hour]
ε_{sc}	MSU self-discharge coefficient [%/hour]
ζ_k	Set of inputs at the k th time interval,
	$\zeta_k = [\xi_{fcr-,k}, \xi_{fcr+,k}, E_{fcr-,k}, E_{fcr+,k}, \Delta_s E_{fcr,k}, \Delta_t E_{fcr,k}, \xi_{pv,k}, P_{hl,k}, P_{ev,k}, P_{fcr-,k}, P_{fcr+,k}, \rho_{RTPEP,k}, \rho_{RTSEP,k}, \rho_{RTPPAP,k}, \rho_{RTPEUP,k}, \rho_{RTSEUP,k}, \rho_{RTSEUP,k}, \rho_{SISP,k}, \rho_{LISP,k}]$
η_{ad}	AC/DC converter efficiency [%]
η_{ddb} (η_{dds})	Battery (SC) DC/DC converter efficiency [%]
θ_{bt}	Fraction of life consumed or cumulated aging rate of an MBU [p.u.]
κ_i	Ratio of operation and maintenance cost vs. initial investment cost for the i th component of the PV household-prosumer [%]
λ	Scale factor
$\xi_{fcr-,k}$ and $\xi_{fcr+,k}$	Downward- and upward- FCR power availability factor at any time period k at the country level (base power: annual maximum FCR power) [p.u.]
$\xi_{pv,k}$	Normalized PV power at any time period k of an MPVU (base power P_{pv}) [p.u.]
$\rho_{RTPEP,k}$ ($\rho_{RTSEP,k}$)	Real-time purchasing(selling) energy price at any time period k in the respective real-time pricing scenario [€/kWh]
$\rho_{RTPPAP,k}$ ($\rho_{RTSPAP,k}$)	Real-time purchasing(selling) power availability price at any time period k [€/kWh]
$\rho_{RTPEUP,k}$ ($\rho_{RTSEUP,k}$)	Real-time purchasing(selling) energy utilization price at any time period k [€/kWh]
$\rho_{SISP,k}$ ($\rho_{LISP,k}$)	Real-time short(long) imbalance settlement price at any time period k [€/kWh]
χ_{bt}^{rat}	Rated DOD of an MBU [%]
χ_{sc}^{rat}	Rated DOD of an MSU [%]
Ω_{ad}	Number of MADUs installed in the AC/DC converter
Ω_{ddb}	Number of MDDDBUs installed in the battery converter
Ω_{dds}	Number of MDDDSUs installed in the supercapacitor converter
$(\lambda, k) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$	
$a_i(n)[A_i(n)]$	Approximation
2^n	Number of data points in the sampled signal
$C_{EE,a}$ ($C_{EE,k}$)	Annual (at any time period k) net income from energy exchange of the PV household-prosumer with the grid ([€/year]), (€/period)
$C_{FCR,a}$ ($C_{FCR,k}$)	Annual (at any time period k) net income from FCR provision of the PV household-prosumer to the utility grid [€/year], ([€/period])
$(C_{I,a}^i, C_I^i)$	(Annual) investment cost of the i th minimum unit ([€/year]), [€/unit]
$i \in \{ad, ddb, dds, pv, bt, sc\}$	
$\{C_{I,a}^i\} \{C_{O\&M,a}^i\}$	Total cost of {initial investment} (operation and maintenance) [replacement] for the PV household-
$[C_{R,a}^i]$	Prosumer(€/year)
$(C_{O\&M,a}^i, C_{O\&M}^i)$	(Annual) operation and maintenance cost of the i th minimum unit ([€/year]), [€/unit]
$i \in \{ad, ddb, dds, pv, bt, sc\}$	
$(C_{R,a}^i, C_{R,i \in \{bt\}}^i)$	(Annual) replacement cost of the i th minimum unit ([€/year]), [€/unit]
d	Nominal discount rate [%]
$d_i(n)[D_i(n)]$	Detail
DOD	Depth of discharge [%]

$e_{fcr,k}$ ($e_{fcr+,k}$)	Cumulated stored(released) FCR energy for the PV household-prosumer [MFCRU] at any period k [kWh]
$[E_{fcr,k}$ ($E_{fcr+,k}$)]	
f_g	Grid frequency
f_s	Sampling frequency
g	Expected annual inflation [%]
$H_{e,i}$	i th equality constraint
$H_{ine,i}$	i th in-equality constraint
J	Discrete-time cost and revenue objective function(or annual NPV) [€/year]
$LE_{bt}^{t_1}$ ($LE_{sc}^{t_1}$)	Beginning energy of MBU (MSU) [kWh]
$LE_{bt}^{t_2}$ ($LE_{sc}^{t_2}$)	End energy of MBU (MSU) [kWh]
$LE_{bt,k}^{lo}$	Lower energy of MBU achieved by the full upward regulation at any time period k [kWh]
$LE_{bt,k}^{up}$	Upper battery energy of MBU achieved by the full downward regulation at any time period k [kWh]
LE_{bt}^{max} (LE_{sc}^{max})	Maximum energy of MBU (MSU) [kWh]
$LCOE$	Levelized cost of energy for prosumer [€/kWh]
n_{min}	Minimum number of decomposition levels
N_b	Calendar lifetime
N_{ine}	Numbers of inequality constraints
N_t	Number of sampling intervals in a year
$NC_{rep_{bt}}$	Number of battery replacements during system lifetime
$N_{i \in \{pv, bt, sc, ad, ddb, dds\}}$	i th minimum unit lifetime [year]
$N_{\theta_{sc}^{max}}$	MBU lifetime according to maximum cumulated aging rate [year]
N_p	PV household-prosumer lifetime [years]
P_{ad}	Rated power of an MADU [kW]
P_{bt-}^{max} (P_{bt+}^{max})	Maximum charge(discharge) power for an MBU [kW]
P_c	Contracted power from the electric mains [kW]
P_{ddb}	Rated power of an MDDBU [kW]
P_{dds}	Rated power of an MDDSU [kW]
$P_{ev,k}$	EVCL at any time period k [kW]
P_{fcr}	Prequalified power capacity of an MFCRU [kW]
$P_{g-,k}$ ($P_{g+,k}$)	Grid power output (input) at any time period k [kW]
$P_{fcr,k}$ ($P_{fcr+,k}$)	Downward-FCR (upward-FCR) power in the PV household-prosumer at any period k [kW]
$p_{fcr,t}$ ($p_{fcr+,t}$)	Downward-FCR (upward-FCR) power in the PV household-prosumer on a 10^{-3} s basis [kW]
$P_{hl,k}$	HCL at any time period k [kW]
P_{sc-}^{max} (P_{sc+}^{max})	Maximum charge(discharge) power for an MSU [kW]
P_{pv}	Rated power of an MPVU [kW]
$P_{pv,k}$	PV power for the PV household-prosumer at any period k [kW]
$r_{O\&M}$	Annual escalation rate of the operation and maintenance cost [%]
r_{pv}	PV degradation rate [%]
$s(t)$	Original signal
$SOC_{ESS}(t)$	SOC of the ESS
t	Time
T	Income tax rate [%]
u	Position factor
$W(\lambda, u)$	Wavelet coefficient

SFCPMS control variables

$\mathbf{P}_{bt,k}$ ($\mathbf{P}_{bt+,k}$) ²	Optimal charge(discharge) power reference for the battery at any period k [kW]
$\mathbf{P}_{sc,k}$ ($\mathbf{P}_{sc+,k}$)	Optimal charge(discharge) power reference for the SC at any period k [kW]
\mathbf{u}_k ($= \mathbf{u}(t_k)$)	Discrete-time SFCPMS control variable vector at the k th time interval, $\mathbf{u}_k = [\mathbf{P}_{bt-,k}, \mathbf{P}_{bt+,k}, \mathbf{P}_{sc-,k}, \mathbf{P}_{sc+,k}]$

¹ Control variables are shown in bold letters

FCREMS control variables

$\mathbf{e}_{sc-,k}$ ($\mathbf{e}_{sc+,k}$)	Optimal downward (upward) FCR energy reference for the SC at any period k [kWh]
\mathbf{v}_k ($= \mathbf{v}(t_k)$)	Discrete-time FCREMS control variable vector at the k th time interval, $\mathbf{v}_k = [\mathbf{e}_{sc-,k}, \mathbf{e}_{sc+,k}]$

Sizing control variables

\mathbf{w}	Sizing control variable vector, $\mathbf{w} = [\Omega_{bt}, \Omega_{sc}, \Omega_{pv}, \Omega_{fcr}]$
Ω_{bt}	Number of MBUs installed in the battery
Ω_{sc}	Number of MSUs installed in the SC
Ω_{pv}	Number of MPVU
Ω_{fcr}	Number of MFCRU

State variables

$Le_{bt,k}$	Battery energy at any time period k [kWh]
$Le_{sc,k}$	SC energy at any time period k [kWh]
x_k ($= x(t_k)$)	Discrete-time state variable vectors at the k th time interval, $x_k = [Le_{bt,k}, Le_{sc,k}]$

Subscripts

a	Annual
app	Approximation
ad	AC/DC converter
bt- (bt+)	To(from) the battery
det	Detail
ddb	DC/DC battery converter
dds	DC/DC supercapacitor converter
EE	Energy exchange with the grid
ESS	Energy storage system
ev	EVCL
FCR	FCR
fcr+/fcr-	FCR to the grid (upward regulation /FCR from the grid (downward regulation)
g- (g+)	To(from) the utility grid
hc	HCL
I	Initial investment
k	Index of time period
max	Maximum
min	Minimum
O&M	Operation and maintenance
ped	PED
ppd	PPD
pv	PVG
R	Replacement
sc- (sc+)	To(from) the supercapacitor

Superscripts

t_1	At the beginning
t_{N_i}	At the end
i	Index of component of the PV household-prosumer
lo	Lower
max	Maximum
min	Minimum
rat	Rated
up	Upper

Abbreviations

AMPSO	Adaptive modified particle swarm optimization
CQGA	Chaotic quantum genetic algorithm
DE	Differential evolutionary
DP	Dynamic programming
DOD	Depth of discharge
ESS	Energy storage system
EV	Electric vehicle

EVCL	EV charging load
GA	Genetic algorithm
GSA	Gravitational search algorithm
FCR	Frequency containment reserve
FCREMS	FCR energy management strategy
FSAPSO	Fuzzy self-adaptive particle swarm optimization
HCL	Household consumption load
HESS	Hybrid energy storage system
LCOE	Levelized cost of energy
MACO	Multi-layer ant colony optimization
MADU	Minimum AC/DC converter unit
MBU	Minimum battery unit
MDDBU	Minimum DC/DC battery converter unit
MDDSU	Minimum DC/DC supercapacitor converter unit
MFCRU	Minimum FCR unit
MINLP	Mixed-integer nonlinear programming
MPSO	Modified particle swarm optimization
MPVU	Minimum PV unit
MSU	Minimum supercapacitor unit
NPV	Net present value
PDF	Probability density function
PED	Prosumer energy demand
PPD	Prosumer power demand
PSO	Particle swarm optimization
PV	Photovoltaic
PVG	PV generation
QP	Quadratic programming
SC	Supercapacitor
SFC	Self-consumption
SFCPMS	SFC power management strategy
SO	System operator
SOC	State of charge
TLBO	Teaching-learning-based optimization
WT	Wavelet transform
WTTLBO	Wavelet transform and teaching-learning-based optimization

1. Introduction

The residential small-scale PV system market to increase self-consumption (SFC) of locally produced electricity has dynamically developed in recent years [1-4]. The declining prices of PV and batteries in combination with rising end-consumer electricity prices have made an increased SFC an attractive option for a PV owner [5]. Given the stochastic behavior of PV systems, this configuration is sustainable only if an integrated PV-storage solution is considered [6-8].

Frequency containment reserve (FCR) is an ancillary service provided by conventional generation to ensure transient stability in power systems. It helps mitigate the fluctuations in the supply and demand, caused by the variation of load or outputs from intermittent renewable resources [9,10]. Because of the fast penetration of renewable energy sources, the provision of FCR from small-medium sized renewable generation has recently come into the spotlight. Furthermore, the latest network codes and standards in the European Union [11- 14] advise or require small distributed generation to synthetically inherit ancillary service functions and then to provide them. Consequently, FCR provision from battery-based PV household-prosumers has been identified as one of the highest value services [15- 22]. HESSs have recently been advocated as excellent candidates for FCR because of their extremely fast ramp rate [9,10,23].

Complementarity between FCR and SFC can be expected, as FCR is a service where power capacity is offered, whereas revenues from SFC are more driven by energy capacity. Within a residential context, some studies have already underlined that combining PV SFC with FCR can substantially increase profitability [15,18,19].

PV household-prosumers participating in SFC and/or FCR demand both high-energy and high-power densities [23- 27]. Therefore, HESSs, which combine the functionalities of supercapacitors (SCs) and batteries, are an effective design to extend battery lifetime, improve efficiency and reduce the sizing and operation cost [23- 27]. A HESS uses the unique SC properties, which offer high power density. This permits the supply of the sharp variations in the demand profile and thus prevents damage to the battery. Meanwhile the battery is oriented to the provision of large time demand requirements.

To effectively protect the battery in the HESS topology [23], component sizing and management strategies should be optimized [23,28- 32]. Moreover, the HESS cost strongly depends on SC hybridization, and excessively high costs are prohibitive to commercial acceptance. It is thus crucial to design methods to optimize sizing and management strategies to fit each prosumer application.

In the literature, various optimization models and frameworks that aim to provide the optimal sizing of battery/SC-based HESSs have also been investigated for electric vehicle (EV) technology [28-30,33,34] and microgrids [35- 38]. However, there are few studies on household-prosumers [39,40] and none on ancillary services. Existing studies merely optimize battery-based energy storage systems (ESSs), e.g. for household-prosumers in [15,41-43], and ancillary services in [15,44,45].

The most frequently used optimization techniques [46,47] for optimally sizing previous ESSs are directed search based methods and heuristic methods. Directed search-based methods [44,42] include mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) [38], dynamic programming (DP) [30,43], and Pontryagin's minimum principle method [28,29]. In contrast, heuristic methods comprise neural networks [36] and population-based algorithms. Regarding the population-based heuristic algorithms, the two most important groups are evolutionary algorithms (e.g., genetic algorithm [GA] [33,37,41,45], and simulated annealing [35,39]) and swarm intelligence-based algorithms (e.g., teaching-learning-based optimization (TLBO) [17] and particle swarm optimization [PSO] [35-40]).

In order to signify the economic/performance role of systems that include at least two power or energy sources, an efficient power or energy management strategy is needed. The power or energy splitting among different sources can significantly influence overall dynamic performance, including equivalent consumption, system component lifetime, and overall cost. The optimal management problem is to find a power or energy sequence over time for each independent source as a control variable which minimizes some predefined objective function. In this regard, the literature on EVs [28,29,31,32-34,48-55], microgrids [15,35,38,58- 70], household-prosumers [41,43,71], and ancillary service applications [44,45,72- 78], support that power or energy management strategies can be divided into three categories.

The first category involves an engineering-intuition control, which determines control laws based on rules [31,35,38,55,58,59,73,74,78], or predictive models based on artificial neural networks [77], fuzzy logic [33,56,60], wavelet transform (WT) [56,60,61], among others. This type of strategies are based on a set of simplified assumptions that are easy to implement and computationally fast. However, they are problem specific and may not provide the optimal global solution for complex engineering optimization problems.

In comparison, the second and third categories include the optimization methods most commonly used because they can find the globally optimal solution based on a finite-horizon optimization. More specifically, the second category entails theoretical methods such as DP [30-32,34,43,48-50,54,72,76]. Nonetheless, significant work has been done for other theoretical methods, such as the interior point optimizer method [75], robust optimization [73], CPLEX-optimizer [71], convex programming [31], and heuristic methods. These heuristic methods include gravitational search algorithm (GSA) [64], multi-layer ant colony optimization (MACO) [65], GA [41,48,69,70], chaotic quantum GA (CQGA) [62], PSO [51,52], adaptive modified PSO (AMPSO) [66], TLBO [17], and artificial neural networks [53]. In addition, some authors solved their proposed model by means of hybrid optimization methods, such as fuzzy self-adaptive PSO (FSAPSO) [67], quadratic programming (QP) together with PSO [63], differential evolutionary (DE) and modified PSO (MPSO) algorithms [68]. The third category includes Pontryagin's minimum principle.

The most efficient optimization method used to solve power or energy management strategies is DP, which is regarded as the absolute optimization method. The method of Pontryagin's minimum principle is nearly good as that of DP but it has the advantage of being more flexible [28,29,31,54,56,57]. The heuristic optimization methods can effectively explore the global optimal region. Furthermore, these methods are less dependent on problem formulations and have the optimizing capability of black-box systems. Of these methods, TLBO [17] outperforms population-based heuristic algorithms. Since the TLBO algorithm was introduced in 2011, several modifications have been proposed by researchers to avoid being trapped by local minima. For example, references [79,80] proposed new variants for improving its performance.

In this context, given the large computational cost of DP [81] and to balance the advantages of the of rule-based and theoretical control strategies applied to power or energy management, this paper proposes a new hybrid meta-heuristic control framework based on the Haar WT algorithm (predictive model) and the TLBO heuristic method (theoretical model) that deals with the management strategies as well as sizing.

Most of the previously mentioned power strategies have been used to deal with systems of double power sources (e.g., main source and battery or SC). However, when there are three sources (e.g., main source, battery, and SC), the two-dimensional power management optimization was only assessed in EV applications [28,29,49,50,57]. In that case, the optimization problem included one degree of freedom and two control variables, and associated state variables, in the power management design process.

Some of these articles coincide that component sizing and power management are two problems usually coupled together, and thus should be studied in greater depth. In an effort to investigate interactions, two-dimensional optimization methods have become an important research focus. Thus, references [28,29,30,32] propose an integrated optimization approach to determine the best system component sizing and power management.

Data temporal granularity of input series (i.e., profiles of household consumption load [HCL] and PV generation [PVG]) and thus the selected time-step resolution for state and control variables have a crucial impact on the results of the optimization algorithms. Consequently, the component sizing such as the battery in PV prosumers [8,82] changed because of inputs that are known to fluctuate at a temporal high-resolution (i.e., interval 0.01–10 Hz [23]). As longer time-step resolutions were envisaged, the input dynamics became increasingly ill-suited, resulting in the underestimation of battery aging [83] and an overestimation of sizing [82] and SFC ratios [8,23]. This meant that it was necessary to discretize the state and control variables at a fine level to provide an accurate picture of such changes in the level of ESS. Nonetheless, there is a trade-off between the computational burden and accuracy, which are determined by this discrete time-step [84].

To date, a major shortcoming is the fact that such inputs have not been adjusted to temporal high-resolution. Most of the examples mentioned, such as [4,31,38- 42,71,73] used hourly or even 30-min time-steps [31], which did not provide accurate results. Moreover, quite a few papers evaluated the bias from the use of coarse-grained data when only calculating the household performance. The resulting picture is ambiguous. Reference [85] concluded that five-minute time-steps provided a good balance between accuracy and the burden of data size, whereas [82] showed that using hourly data led to large biases compared to one-minute data. However, coarser data could be sufficient for household aggregation [86]. A shorter fluctuation at the granularity of just 4-seconds was investigated in [87]. Reference [88] found the impact of time-resolution was significantly influenced by the system configurations.

Still another shortcoming is the way to explicitly include the most temporal details of a full time data series. Thus, most studies used time slices, more specifically, a reduced timespan chosen to characterize key aspects of temporal variability, for example, covering weekdays and weekends, different times of day, and different seasons. In this way, the time horizon envisaged was typically restricted to minutes [28-30,32,49,50,57], a few hours [31,71,74] or a few days [42,73], which can be extremely overoptimistic when predicting cost.

While the current trend is to use more temporally granular data sets in household applications, the influence of temporal granularity has yet to be analyzed using a comprehensive and high-resolution data set. Furthermore, the application of HESSs for providing FCR and PV SFC in household-prosumers is relatively new and has a high potential market. Therefore, to the best of our knowledge, the complementary study of services such as FCR and PV SFC in household-prosumer applications on the

basis of a joint optimization of power and energy management and component sizing has not as yet been reported in the literature. A more in-depth investigation of this problem is thus needed.

For this purpose, we have thus expanded our previous work on battery-based PV household-prosumers [17], and have explicitly adopted not only the power management and sizing [28,29] but also the energy management required for FCR provision and application to an HESS. This was carried out by means of a hybrid meta-heuristic optimization algorithm which accounts for an increased number of optimization variables, especially applied to several service scenarios. This algorithm enables an accurate assessment of service complementarity, especially when different temporal data granularity is considered.

This study addressed the following research questions:

- How can time resolution be efficiently reduced by balancing the accuracy of the optimal sizing and management with the computational load?
- Does service complementarity affect component sizing, and mainly the HESS?
- What impact do optimal management strategies have on the effective cycle of the battery to extend its lifespan?

To answer these questions, this research developed a novel high-resolution domestic multi-power-energy model with several key features that have never been previously combined. This new model includes the following features: (i) separation of multi-energy services from multi-power inputs; (ii) accurate representation of HESS (e.g. battery degradation model) and converter efficiencies; (iii) high granularity. Furthermore, a hybrid meta-heuristic optimization algorithm based on WT and TLBO (WTTLBO) was used to obtain the best solution in the four-dimensional, non-linear, non-convex, and mixed-integer optimization problem. This problem deals with power and energy management and component sizing. The algorithm is designed so that it can be flexibly adapted in terms of the number of discrete states to suit the input profiles defined in different time discretizations. Its main advantage is that it provides a globally optimal solution, with a relatively non-excessive computational load stemming from the very high number of state and control variables.

A case study using different data granularity for a PV prosumer in Spain showed the optimal results for several service scenarios. These results provide valuable insights into the influence of data granularity and service complementarity. The ultimate goal of this research was to determine the optimal granularity and the economic feasibility of providing complementary services.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 explains the design and modelling of the PV household-prosumer, and Section 3 quantitatively describes the economic modelling. The power and energy management are then discussed in Section 4, Section 5 deals with the optimization methodology, after which, the input data are provided in Section 6. The simulation and case studies in Section 7 are followed by the concluding remarks in Section 8.

2. The PV household-prosumer

The PV household-prosumer consists of a PV system, an HESS, DC/DC and DC/AC converters and residential loads (EV charging load –EVCL– and HCL), as shown in Fig. 1. The PV runs as the main power source to meet the load. The HESS serves as an energy storage site to compensate power fluctuations whereas the LV AC grid is used as a backup. The PV prosumer also provides FCR. Power and energy arrows are used as a reference throughout the paper.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the PV household-prosumer.

2.1. Framework for assessing FCR from household-prosumers

The methodology for technically assessing the FCR power and its activation was based on the flowchart in Fig. 2. Firstly, the power-frequency characteristic [89] for FCR had been previously modelled by the authors in PV-battery systems [9] and EVs [10]. This research adapted the models in [9,10] to the new household-prosumer context. Accordingly, the novel model disabled PV power in [9] or bidirectional charging in [10], and only maintained the frequency control in charge of providing FCR. The input data included grid frequency, f_g , FCR power availability (downward- and upward- FCR power availability factor at the country level, $\xi_{fcr-,k}$, $\xi_{fcr+,k}$), and several parameters that defined the ESS behavior and its energy management. The frequency control module, on a 10^{-3} -s basis, generated the requirement of active power based on frequency. The downward-FCR or upward-FCR power, $p_{fcr-}(t)$ (or $p_{fcr+}(t)$) accounted for both the droop and inertial response. The operation simulation module of ESS calculated the energy balance and its level management for every time-step Δ_t . Accordingly the cumulated stored, released, shortage and surplus FCR energy ($E_{fcr-,k}$, $E_{fcr+,k}$, $\Delta_s E_{fcr-,k}$, $\Delta_l E_{fcr+,k}$) was able to be evaluated by integrating the FCR power based on the state of charge (SOC) of the ESS, $SOC_{ESS}(t)$.

Fig. 2. Structure of the FCR simulation mode for a MFCRU.

2.2. Power and energy model for FCR

FCR markets in Europe require participants to provide constant FCR power for the duration of a contract. The time slice varies from 0.5 h to one week [90]. Therefore, any prosumer aggregator should ensure that the sum of effective FCR power capacities remains constant during this period. Accordingly, the FCR power of a prosumer should remain constant for each time slice. Nonetheless, this signal was modulated by the FCR power availability factor at the country level ($\xi_{fcr-,k}, \xi_{fcr+,k}$) to generate an appropriate prosumer FCR power signal (downward-FCR $p_{fcr-,k}$, upward-FCR $p_{fcr+,k}$) according to the prequalified MFCRU capacity, P_{fcr} , and the number of MFCRUs, Ω_{fcr} [15]:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{fcr-,k} &= \Omega_{fcr} \cdot \xi_{fcr-,k} \cdot P_{fcr} \\ p_{fcr+,k} &= \Omega_{fcr} \cdot \xi_{fcr+,k} \cdot P_{fcr} \quad \forall k \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The cumulated stored, released, shortage and surplus FCR energies for the PV household-prosumer are given from relevant energies of a MFCRU in Section 2.1, appropriately adapted by availability factors and the number of MFCRUs:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{fcr-,k} &= \Omega_{fcr} \cdot \xi_{fcr-,k} \cdot E_{fcr-,k} \\ e_{fcr+,k} &= \Omega_{fcr} \cdot \xi_{fcr+,k} \cdot E_{fcr+,k} \quad \forall k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_s e_{fcr,k} &= \Omega_{fcr} \cdot \xi_{fcr+,k} \cdot \Delta_s E_{fcr,k} \\ \Delta_l e_{fcr,k} &= \Omega_{fcr} \cdot \xi_{fcr-,k} \cdot \Delta_l E_{fcr,k}, \quad \forall k \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

As was observed in our study, the assessment of FCR energy occurs every 10^{-3} -s whereas the technical and resulting economic basepoint is set every k -th time-step.

2.3. PV power model

The normalized PV power of an MPVU, $\xi_{pv, k}$, is a function of the irradiance, ambient temperature, and PV system efficiency as explained in [91]. The PV power for the PV household-prosumer can thus be defined according to the MPVU power, P_{pv} , and the number of units, Ω_{pv} :

$$P_{pv, k} = \Omega_{pv} \cdot \xi_{pv, k} \cdot P_{pv}, \quad \forall k \quad (4)$$

2.4. Energy model of the battery

The energy model of the battery is formulated in the discrete-time domain from the state variable battery energy at the k th state ($Le_{bt, k}$), and the state transition from the $(k-1)$ th to k th state. This is determined by two of the control variables of the SFC power management strategy (SFCPMS) ($p_{bt, k}, p_{bt+, k}$), the control variables of the FCR energy management strategy (FCREMS) ($v_k = [e_{sc-, k}, e_{sc+, k}]$), and one of the sizing control variables (Ω_{fer}) as well as some exogenous inputs ($\xi_{fer-, k}, E_{fer-, k}, \xi_{fer+, k}, E_{fer+, k}$):

$$Le_{bt, k} = Le_{bt, k-1} - \varepsilon_{bt} \cdot Le_{bt, k-1} + \Delta_t \cdot \left(\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt} \cdot p_{bt-, k} - \frac{p_{bt+, k}}{\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt}} \right) + \left(\eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt} \left[\eta_{ad} \cdot \Omega_{fer} \cdot \xi_{fer-, k} \cdot E_{fer-, k} - \frac{e_{sc-, k}}{\eta_{dds} \cdot \eta_{sc}} \right] - \frac{1}{\eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt}} \left[\frac{\Omega_{fer} \cdot \xi_{fer+, k} \cdot E_{fer+, k}}{\eta_{ad}} - \frac{e_{sc+, k}}{\eta_{dds} \cdot \eta_{sc}} \right] \right), \quad \forall k \quad (5)$$

Component losses were modelled by efficiencies which depended on the normalized input/output power [92]. To ensure that battery energy remains available for the FCR, we have to adapt the energy limits between which the battery can perform FCR so that it is smaller than the designed limits. According to requirements for FCR-units with limited energy reservoirs [93-95], these units need to be capable of providing the full prequalified FCR power for at least 30 minutes. Consequently, the upper battery energy achieved by the full downward regulation for any time period k ($Le_{bt, k}^{up}$) is calculated by:

$$Le_{bt, k}^{up} = Le_{bt, k-1} - \varepsilon_{bt} \cdot Le_{bt, k-1} + \Delta_t \cdot \left(\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt} \cdot p_{bt-, k} - \frac{p_{bt+, k}}{\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt}} \right) + \eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt} \cdot \Omega_{fer} \cdot P_{fer} \cdot 0.5, \quad \forall k \quad (6)$$

For full upward regulation, the lower battery energy for any time period k , $Le_{bt, k}^{lo}$, is as follows:

$$Le_{bt, k}^{lo} = Le_{bt, k-1} - \varepsilon_{bt} \cdot Le_{bt, k-1} + \Delta_t \cdot \left(\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt} \cdot p_{bt-, k} - \frac{p_{bt+, k}}{\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt}} \right) - \frac{\Omega_{fer} \cdot P_{fer} \cdot 0.5}{\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{ddb} \cdot \eta_{bt}}, \quad \forall k \quad (7)$$

By making these limits dependent on the time k , they can be shaped towards the maximum expected amount of the full FCR activation.

2.4.1. Battery degradation model

This section is based on the battery lifetime modelling developed by the authors. A more in-depth explanation of this model can be found in [17], which cannot be included here because of space limitations. The model of life consumed or aging rate of a minimum battery unit (MBU) for a given discharge cycle is based on the charge/discharge power rate and depth of discharge (DOD). The DOD at each cycle is obtained from the battery SOC using the Rain Flow method.

2.5. Energy model of the SC

The energy model of the SC is formulated throughout the state variable SC energy ($Le_{sc,k}$) by a general charge balance that accounts for its energy inputs and outputs. This is determined by two of the control variables of the SFCPMS ($p_{sc-,k}, p_{sc+,k}$), the control variables of the FCREMS ($v_k = [e_{sc-,k}, e_{sc+,k}]$):

$$Le_{sc,k} = Le_{sc,k-1} - \varepsilon_{sc} \cdot Le_{sc,k-1} + \Delta_t \cdot \left(\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{dds} \cdot \eta_{sc} \cdot p_{sc-,k} - \frac{p_{sc+,k}}{\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{dds} \cdot \eta_{sc}} \right) + (e_{sc-,k} - e_{sc+,k}), \quad \forall k \quad (8)$$

2.6. Constraints

Constraints were classified in the following four categories: (i) global power balance, which includes the constraint concerning the general power balance at the AC link; (ii) sizing control variables within a feasible sizing range; (iii) partial power balances, which include specific constraints that control the power operation of the HESS and converters while providing FCR and SFC; (iv) HESS energy balances, which are composed of all the constraints that manage the energy charging/discharging on the HESS, including its response to FCR provision. Additionally, appropriate variables were constrained as non-negative.

2.6.1. Equality constraints

When solving the optimization problem, it is crucial that the power balance at the AC link be satisfied throughout the time horizon. Thus, constraint (9) is the power balance equation of the generated power and the consumed power in each time interval k .

$$\begin{aligned} P_{g+,k} - P_{g-,k} + P_{bt+,k} - P_{bt-,k} + P_{sc+,k} - P_{sc-,k} - P_{ppd,k} &= 0 \\ P_{ppd,k} &= P_{hl,k} + P_{ev,k} - P_{pv,k} \end{aligned} \quad \forall k \quad (9)$$

2.6.2. In-equality constraints

The following set of equations represents constraints on the sizing control variables $-w = [\Omega_{bt}, \Omega_{sc}, \Omega_{pv}, \Omega_{fcr}]$:-

$$\begin{aligned}
0 \leq \Omega_{bt} &\leq \Omega_{bt}^{\max} \\
0 \leq \Omega_{sc} &\leq \Omega_{sc}^{\max} \\
0 \leq \Omega_{pv} &\leq \Omega_{pv}^{\max} \\
0 \leq \Omega_{fcr} &\leq \Omega_{fcr}^{\max}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

To ensure that the FCR is always available, both power and energy must remain within a feasible operational range at each time instance. Regarding FCR power for the PV household-prosumer, it is necessary to explicitly add hard constraints for the maximum charge (discharge) power in the SC and battery (11)-(12), the rated power of the AC/DC converter (16)-(17), battery DC/DC converter (18)-(19), SC DC/DC converter (20)-(21) and the contracted power from electric mains, P_c , (22)-(23). Regarding FCR energy, hard energy constraints in the battery (24)-(25) have been added.

Although the set of in-equality constraints for the SC and battery are the same, the numerical values differ significantly. The set of operational constraints for each storage technology (x) are shown in (11) to (14) (i.e., for the battery, replace x with bt , and for the SC replace x with sc). Constraints are applied to the power and energy. For the SC, the input and output power are constrained based on the standard method in [96]. For the battery, the maximum charge (discharge) power is based on the maximum *C-rate*. The constraint on maximum/minimum energy bounds for the battery and SC is shown in (13). From the standpoint of the charging/discharging process sustainability, it is frequent to set the energy to be equal at the beginning and end of the time (t_1, t_{N_t}) (14). The positivity of SFCPMS control variables $-\mathbf{u}_k = [p_{bt-,k}, p_{bt+,k}, p_{sc-,k}, p_{sc+,k}]$ and state variables $-\mathbf{x}_k = [Le_{bt-,k}, Le_{sc-,k}]$ is represented in (15).

$$p_{x-,k} + p_{fcr-,k} \leq \Omega_x \cdot P_{x-}^{\max}, \forall k \tag{11}$$

$$p_{x+,k} + p_{fcr+,k} \leq \Omega_x \cdot P_{x+}^{\max}, \forall k \tag{12}$$

$$\Omega_x \cdot LE_x^{\max} \left(1 - \frac{\chi_x^{rat}}{100}\right) \leq Le_{x,k} \leq \Omega_x \cdot LE_x^{\max}, \forall k \tag{13}$$

$$Le_x^{t_1} = \Omega_x \cdot LE_x^{t_1} = Le_x^{t_{N_t}} = \Omega_x \cdot LE_x^{t_{N_t}} \tag{14}$$

$$p_{x-,k}, p_{x+,k}, Le_{x,k} \geq 0, \forall k \tag{15}$$

The in-equality constraints of power for the AC/DC converter and the SC and battery DC/DC converters are nevertheless different. Equations (16) and (17) state the rated power limit for the AC/DC converter; (18) and (19) pertain to the rated battery AC/DC converter power; and (20) and (21) are focused on the rated SC AC/DC converter power. In all cases, the power limit of each converter is based on the rated power of the relevant unit and the number of units:

$$p_{bt-,k} + p_{sc-,k} + p_{fcr-,k} \leq \Omega_{ad} \cdot P_{ad}, \forall k \tag{16}$$

$$p_{bt+,k} + p_{sc+,k} + p_{fcr+,k}^j \leq \Omega_{ad} \cdot P_{ad}, \forall k \tag{17}$$

$$p_{bt-,k} + p_{fcr-,k} \leq \Omega_{ddb} \cdot P_{ddb}, \forall k \tag{18}$$

$$p_{bt+,k} + p_{fcr+,k}^j \leq \Omega_{ddb} \cdot P_{ddb}, \forall k \tag{19}$$

$$P_{sc-,k} + P_{fcr-,k} \leq \Omega_{dds} \cdot P_{dds}, \quad \forall k \quad (20)$$

$$P_{sc+,k} + P_{fcr+,k}^j \leq \Omega_{dds} \cdot P_{dds}, \quad \forall k \quad (21)$$

Grid constraints (22)-(23) ensure that the total amount of the power exchange with the AC LV grid does not exceed the maximum contracted power from electric mains, P_c :

$$P_{g+,k} + P_{frc+,k} \leq P_c, \quad \forall k \quad (22)$$

$$P_{g-,k} + P_{frc-,k} \leq P_c, \quad \forall k \quad (23)$$

Equations (24)-(25) constrain the hard upper/lower battery energy, $Le_{bt,k}^{up}, Le_{bt,k}^{lo}$. This ensures that there is always a level of reserve in the battery to respond to the maximum change in system frequency, as defined by the system operator (SO) for any time period:

$$Le_{bt,k}^{up} \leq \Omega_{bt} \cdot LE_{bt}^{\max}, \quad \forall k \quad (24)$$

$$Le_{bt,k}^{lo} \geq \Omega_{bt} \cdot LE_{bt}^{\max} \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_{bt}^{rat}}{100} \right), \quad \forall k \quad (25)$$

The following set of equations represent restrictions on the FCREMS control variables $-v_k = [e_{sc-,k}, e_{sc+,k}]$ —which are capped by the FCR energy specified for the PV household-prosumer ($e_{fcr+,k}, e_{fcr-,k}$) by the actual frequency response:

$$0 \leq e_{sc+,k} \leq \frac{e_{fcr+,k}}{\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{dds}}, \quad \forall k \quad (26)$$

$$0 \leq e_{sc-,k} \leq \frac{\eta_{ad} \cdot e_{fcr-,k}}{\eta_{dds}}, \quad \forall k$$

3. Economic modelling

The financial profitability of the PV prosumer is assessed by the net present value (NPV) and the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) that includes the reliability of the prosumer's facility configuration to meet the load demand and the FCR provision.

3.1. Initial investment cost

The annual upfront capital cost $C_{l,a}$ is given by:

$$C_{l,a} = \sum_i C_{l,a}^i, \quad i \in \{ad, ddb, dds, pv, bt, sc\} \quad (27)$$

This cost is based on available data such as the energy and power specific capital cost ($C_{l,a}^i$):

$$C_{l,a}^i = \frac{\Omega_i \cdot C_l^i}{N_i}, \quad i \in \{pv, bt, sc\} \quad (28)$$

$$C_{l,a}^i = \frac{\Omega_i \cdot C_l^i}{N_i}, \quad i \in \{ad, ddb, dds\}$$

3.2. Operation and maintenance cost

The annual present value of the operation and maintenance cost for i th each component of the PV prosumer's facility, $C_{O\&M,a}^i$, is:

$$C_{O\&M,a}^i = \frac{1}{N_p} \cdot C_{O\&M}^i \cdot (1-T) \cdot \frac{K_p^i \left(1 - (K_p^i)^{N_p}\right)}{1 - K_p^i}, \quad i \in \{ad, ddb, dds, pv, bt, sc\} \quad (29)$$

where:

$$K_p^i = \frac{1+g}{1+d} \left(1 + r_{O\&M}^i\right) \quad (30)$$

$$C_{O\&M}^i = \kappa_j \cdot C_I^i, \quad i \in \{ad, ddb, dds, pv, bt, sc\} \quad (31)$$

$$C_{O\&M,a} = \sum_i C_{O\&M,a}^i, \quad i \in \{ad, ddb, dds, pv, bt, sc\} \quad (32)$$

The operation and maintenance cost for the PV prosumer's facility is:

$$C_{O\&M,a} = \sum_i C_{O\&M,a}^i, \quad i \in \{ad, ddb, dds, pv, bt, sc\} \quad (33)$$

3.3. Replacement cost

The battery will eventually need to be replaced because of degradation during usage. The number of battery replacements during the lifetime of the facility, $NC_{rep_{bt}}$ is:

$$NC_{rep_{bt}} = Integer \left(\frac{Lifetime_{PV \text{ household-prosumer}}}{Lifetime_{battery}} \right) = Integer \left(\frac{N_p}{\min(N_{\theta_{bt}^{max}}, N_{bt})} \right) \quad (34)$$

The battery may reach the end of its useful life in two ways. It may either reach a maximum number of years from the time of its installation N_{bt} (calendar lifetime), or have a maximum cumulated aging rate ($\theta_{bt} = \theta_{bt}^{max}$) at year $N_{\theta_{bt}^{max}}$ (cycling lifetime), before reaching its maximum number of years ($N_{\theta_{bt}^{max}} < N_{bt}$).

Let us define $C_{R,a}$ as the net present cost of the battery replacement, namely, its replacement battery cost minus the revenues at the end of the facility lifetime due to the remaining battery lifespan:

$$C_{R,a} = C_{R,a}^{bt} = \sum_s^{NC_{rep_{bt}}} \frac{(1+g)^{s \cdot \min(N_{\theta_{bt}^{max}}, N_{bt})}}{(1+d)^{s \cdot \min(N_{\theta_{bt}^{max}}, N_{bt})}} \cdot C_{I,a}^{bt} - \left(N_p - NC_{rep_{bt}} \cdot \min(N_{\theta_{bt}^{max}}, N_{bt}) \right) \frac{(1+g)^{s \cdot N_p}}{(1+d)^{s \cdot N_p}} \cdot C_{I,a}^{bt} \quad (35)$$

3.4. Net income from energy exchange

The incomes associated with purchasing/selling electricity from/to the grid are computed on the assumption that different prices apply to energy purchasing/selling ($\rho_{RTPEP,k}, \rho_{RTSEP,k}$) on a spot intraday market. Therefore, the net income is split between a cost due to energy purchasing and a revenue due to

energy selling. Every k th time the model activates a power transaction $(p_{g^+,k}, p_{g^-,k})$ and the net income, $C_{EE,k}$, is calculated as:

$$C_{EE,k} = \begin{cases} \rho_{RTPEP,k} \cdot \Delta_t \cdot p_{g^+,k} & p_{g^+,k} \geq 0 \\ -\rho_{RTSEP,k} \cdot \Delta_t \cdot p_{g^-,k} & p_{g^-,k} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

As price on the real-time energy market is assumed to be constant during 2019, the present worth of the net income on an annual basis is:

$$C_{EE,a} = \frac{1}{N_p} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{n=N_p} \frac{(1+g)^n}{(1+d)^n} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{k=N_t} C_{EE,k} = \frac{q \cdot (1-q^{N_p})}{N_p \cdot (1-q)} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{k=N_t} C_{EE,k} \quad (37)$$

where:

$$q = \frac{1+g}{1+d} \quad (38)$$

3.5. Net income from FCR provision

The PV household-prosumer is paid for FCR power availability (downward-FCR $p_{fcr-,k}$, upward-FCR $p_{fcr+,k}$) [97]. In other words, the remuneration is proportional to FCR power and the tendering period. Moreover, it is paid for the actual amount of FCR energy supplied ($e_{fcr+,k}$) or consumed ($e_{fcr-,k}$) [97]. Nonetheless, when the SOC in the HESS is too low or too high, it may fail to supply or absorb the amount of FCR energy requested by the system operator (SO) during the time interval. In this case, the prosumer receives a penalty that is proportional to the shortage of FCR energy ($\Delta_s e_{fcr,k}$) at a short imbalance settlement price ($\rho_{SISP,k}$). When there is a surplus, it receives the long imbalance settlement price ($\rho_{LISP,k}$) [98]. We then compute the net income from the FCR provision ($C_{FCR,k}$) with 80% of the aggregator's gain [15] over discretized values of power and energy buying/selling (first and second term) and long or short positions (third term):

$$C_{FCR,k} = 0.8 * \left[\left(\rho_{RTPPAP,k} \cdot p_{fcr-,k} + \rho_{RTSPAP,k} \cdot p_{fcr+,k} \right) + \left(\rho_{RTSEUP,k} \cdot e_{fcr+,k} - \rho_{RTPEUP,k} \cdot e_{fcr-,k} \right) \right] - \left(\rho_{LISP,k} \cdot \Delta_s e_{fcr,k} + \rho_{SISP,k} \cdot \Delta_s e_{fcr,k} \right) \quad (39)$$

The present worth of the net income from FCR provision on an annual basis is:

$$C_{FCR,a} = \frac{1}{N_p} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{n=N_p} \frac{(1+g)^n}{(1+d)^n} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{k=N_t} C_{FCR,k} = \frac{q \cdot (1-q^{N_p})}{N_p \cdot (1-q)} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{k=N_t} C_{FCR,k} \quad (40)$$

4. Power and energy management

The battery and SC hybridization when managing power and energy can only take advantage of the characteristics of each source if effective power and energy management strategies are modelled. The power management strategy (or energy strategy) should set two objectives: (i) the power (or energy)-

splitting objective on a multi-time scale and (ii), the constraint objective of the feedback SOC. Accordingly, this paper models an integrated strategy based on a Harr WT and theoretical TLBO method for power and energy management. The three power sources are involved are the AC grid, battery, and SC. Therefore, one degree of freedom and two state control variables model the SFCPMS design. In contrast, two energy sources in the HESS involve one degree of freedom and one state variable in the FCREMS design.

The basic principle of the WT-based power/energy management strategy is to supply a transient signal of the prosumer power demand (PPD) or prosumer energy demand (PED) from the SC, while supplying the corresponding base signal from the battery. In the WT, an original signal can be decomposed into localized contributions characterized by a scalable modulated time window of varying size. Each contribution represents a portion of the signal with a different frequency. By employing the long windows at low frequencies and short windows at high frequencies, the WT is capable of simultaneously comprehending the time and frequency information without concealing the details of the signal [61]. The discrete WT decomposes a discretized signal into different resolution levels as follows:

$$W(\lambda, u) = \int s(t) \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \psi\left(\frac{t-u}{\lambda}\right) \cdot dt, \quad \lambda = 2^j, \quad u = k \cdot 2^j, \quad (\lambda, k) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \quad (41)$$

Of the different kinds of wavelet, the Haar wavelet has the shortest filter length in the time domain and is the most popular WT type [61]. Meanwhile, the function of extracting transients can still be well implemented without degradation. More details can be found in [97,99].

The three-level Haar WT decomposition and reconstruction are applied in this study on the original discretized signals $s_i(n)$ (PPD and PED profiles i.e., $p_{ppd,k}$, e_{ped-k} , e_{ped+k}) to model the first objective of the integrated power (or energy) management, Fig. 3. Thus, the Haar-WT based strategy uses a low-pass filter $l_0(z)$ and a high-pass filter $h_0(z)$ in the wavelet decomposition structure. The output of the j th high-pass filter is the detail part $d_{j,i}(n)$ and the output of the j th low-pass filter is the approximation part $a_{j,i}(n)$. Similarly, the synthesis filter bank consists of a low-pass and high-pass synthesis filter ($l_1(z)$, $h_1(z)$). The down-sampling and up-sampling method is employed in the decomposition and synthesis processes, respectively. The data size is reduced by half in down-sampling operations while it doubles in up-sampling operations [56].

Fig. 3. Decomposition and reconstruction based on the Harr Wavelet.

The transient signal of the i th PPD profile (or PED profile) $D_i(n)$ is reconstructed by combining the three decomposed detail parts while matching the number of samples of each detail part with up-sampling. Meanwhile, the base signal of the i th PPD profile (or PED profile) $A_i(n)$ is reconstructed from the approximation part achieved after the final decomposition.

By using this Harr WT-based strategy that decomposes the high-frequency and low-frequency components, the independent PPD (or PED) signal can take advantage of the three power sources (or two energy sources).

Adopting only a high-frequency and low-frequency splitting strategy for the PPD (or PED) profile may not be sufficient to regulate the SOCs on the HESS. The battery and SC should have enough power and charge to supply the required PPD and PED and it should also have enough capacity to recover them. The majority of the studies implemented the SOC control through a semi-empirical strategy [55,58-60]. Although this was simple, it did not optimize the power signal. In order to rationally adjust the initial power (or energy) references generated by the Harr WT for the battery and SC, optimal SOC control power (or energy) schedules, computed from the theoretical TLBO method, determined the optimal power (or energy) references of the integrated strategy, such that the SOCs in the battery and SC were recovered at close to their optimal values.

5. Optimization methodology

5.1. Optimization problem approach

The optimization of the component sizing, SFCPMS, and FCREMS for PV household-prosumers is a constrained optimization problem. The discrete-time cost and revenue objective function to be minimized can be formulated as:

$$\text{Minimize } J = \sum_{k=1}^{N_t} F(x_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{w}, \zeta_k, k) \quad (42)$$

where, x_k , \mathbf{u}_k , \mathbf{v}_k , \mathbf{w} , ζ_k , k are the vectors of state variables, SFCPMS control variables, FCREMS control variables, sizing control variables, and inputs, respectively. k represents a time interval.

The prosumer state model is formulated in the discrete-time domain as the set of difference equations (5) and (8). These equations relate the state variable transition from the $k-1$ th to k th state and can be written as follows:

$$x_k = f(x_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{w}, k), \quad k=1, \dots, N_t \quad (43)$$

The initial and final conditions for the state variable vector in (14) can be written as follows:

$$x_1 = x(t_1) = x_{N_t} = x(t_{N_t}) \quad (44)$$

The vectors of the state variables ($x_k = [Le_{bt, k}, Le_{sc, k}]$) and control variables ($[\mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{w}] = [[\mathbf{p}_{bt-, k}, \mathbf{p}_{bt+, k}, \mathbf{p}_{sc-, k}, \mathbf{p}_{sc+, k}], [\mathbf{e}_{sc-, k}, \mathbf{e}_{sc+, k}], [\mathbf{Q}_{bt}, \mathbf{Q}_{sc}, \mathbf{Q}_{pv}, \mathbf{Q}_{fcr}]]$) are explicitly constrained in their domains by the equality and in-equality constraints (hard constraints). The equality constraint $H_{e,i}()$ in (9) can be written as follows:

$$H_{e,i}(\mathbf{u}_k, \zeta_k) = 0, \quad i=1 \quad (45)$$

The in-equality constraints $H_{ine,i}()$ in (10)-(13) and (15)-(26) can be written as follows:

$$H_{ine,i}(\mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{w}, x_k, \zeta_k) \leq 0, \quad i=1, 2, \dots, N_{ine} \quad (46)$$

5.2. Detailed optimization problem formulation

The optimization problem applied to PV household-prosumers is complex since there is a trade-off between different power and energy sources as well as component sizing. Three independent power sources, the AC grid, battery and SC should work simultaneously to meet the PPD. Meanwhile, two independent energy sources, the battery and SC, should fulfil the PED. Accordingly, a HESS power cooperative operation (SFCPMS) is necessary to balance the power inputs and outputs. Furthermore, a HESS energy cooperative operation (FCREMS) is required to balance the energy inputs and outputs. Hence, the discrete-time optimization for the PV household-prosumer with a HESS is a four-dimensional, non-linear, non-convex, and mixed-integer optimization problem. The optimization problem is defined by the vectors of state variables (x_k) and control variables ($[\mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{w}]$), an objective function from (42), a discrete-time state-space model (43), and the corresponding constraints (45) and (46).

Regarding the SFCPMS optimization, the control variables are the charge (or discharge) power reference for the battery and SC $-\mathbf{u}_k = [\mathbf{p}_{bt-, k}, \mathbf{p}_{bt+, k}, \mathbf{p}_{sc-, k}, \mathbf{p}_{sc+, k}]$. Regarding the FCREMS optimization, the control variables are the downward (or upward) FCR energy reference for the SC $-\mathbf{v}_k = [\mathbf{e}_{sc-, k}, \mathbf{e}_{sc+, k}]$. The state variables are battery and SC energy $-x_k = [Le_{bt, k}, Le_{sc, k}]$. Regarding the sizing optimization the control variables are the number of MBUs, MSUs, MPVUs, and MFCRUs $-\mathbf{w} = [\mathbf{Q}_{bt}, \mathbf{Q}_{sc}, \mathbf{Q}_{pv}, \mathbf{Q}_{fcr}]$.

The optimization goal is to find the best sizing $[w]$ together with the optimal SFCPMS $[u_k]$ and FCREMS $[v_k]$ for different power and energy sources that must result in the lowest cost. Therefore, the objective function (42) is expressed in economic terms, and corresponds to the addition of terms expressed as:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{N_t} F(x_k, u_k, v_k, \zeta_k, k) = C_{I,a} + C_{O\&M,a} + C_{R,a} + \frac{q \cdot (1 - q^{N_p})}{N_p \cdot (1 - q)} \cdot \left[\sum_{k=1}^{N_t} C_{EE,k} - C_{FCR,k} \right] \quad (47)$$

The terms in the objective function include all the costs and revenues involved in the project lifetime. They comprise the initial investment cost $C_{I,a}$, (27), operation and maintenance cost $C_{O\&M,a}$, (33), replacement cost $C_{R,a}$, (35), net income from energy exchange at the k th interval $C_{EE,k}$, (37), and net income from FCR provision at the k th interval $C_{FCR,k}$, (40), calculated in Section 3.

LCOE for the PV prosumer is computed as follows [5]:

$$LCOE = \frac{J}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_t} (p_{ev,k} + p_{hl,k})} \quad (48)$$

The search space contains all possibilities such as the following:

$$\Omega_{pv} \in [0, \Omega_{pv}^{\max}], \Omega_{bt} \in [0, \Omega_{bt}^{\max}], \Omega_{sc} \in [0, \Omega_{sc}^{\max}], \Omega_{fer} \in [0, \Omega_{fer}^{\max}],$$

$$p_{bt,k} \in [p_{bt}^{\min}, p_{bt}^{\max}], p_{sc,k} \in [p_{sc}^{\min}, p_{sc}^{\max}], e_{s+,k} \in \left[0, \frac{e_{fer+,k}}{\eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{dds}} \right] \text{ and } e_{s-,k} \in [0, \eta_{ad} \cdot \eta_{dds} \cdot e_{fer-,k}].$$

5.3. Proposed optimization algorithm

Fitting power and energy management in the battery/supercapacitor-based PV household-prosumer is a key issue to improve HESS performance. Furthermore, component sizing is critical to increase the profitability of the asset. Therefore, the optimization in this research involves a four-dimensional, non-linear, non-convex, and mixed-integer optimization problem with quite a large number of constraints, considering the discretized equations at every sampled interval. Integer values in the domain of solutions has been modelled (some of control variables discretized). The nonlinearity of the problem, the non-convex functions in the objective function, and the excessive number of constraints pose additional challenges with multiple local optima. In this context, this paper has proposed a hybrid meta-heuristic optimization algorithm based on the WT algorithm and the TLBO heuristic method that deals with the management strategies as well as sizing.

A more detailed description of the Haar WT algorithm can be found in [62]. The TLBO algorithm proposed was based on [17], but it used a variant for improving its performance. Thus, in teaching phase, a perturbed scheme was applied to prevent that current best solution from being trapped in local minima. Whereas a global crossover strategy was incorporated into the learning phase, which aimed at balancing local and global searching effectively [79].

6. Set of inputs

Experimental data of a residential facility from Jaen, a city in southern Spain, were acquired by smart meters at different granularities from 30 to 0.5-min time intervals (see [23] for details). Data included HCL profiles as well as EVCL and PVG profiles from an EV charging system and a 2.97-kWp PV system, respectively. In order to better compare results, the raw input data were downscaled to Spain-average profiles. Namely, the PV annually yielded 1400-kWh/kWp. Meanwhile, 5450-kWh and 2440-kWh represented the annual average Spanish-household electricity consumption [23,100] and the EV charging electricity for the annual average driving distance in Spain of 13559 km, respectively [100].

Although the PPD data were collected at a granularity ranging from 30 to 0.5-min (30, 20, 10, 5, 2.5, 1, and 0.5-min) over the course of 2019, running the analysis at a 0.5-min time-step for 365 days was not computationally feasible. In order to cluster a representative sample of days, we chose 10 days of each month [101].

Fig. 4a1 and b1 show the PVG and HCL profiles for different granularities for one day in September whereas Fig. 4a2 and b2 represent the annual probability density functions (PDFs). These figures highlight the twofold nature of the HCL, the continuity of roughly 0.45-kW base-load and the intermittent spikes of up to a 5-kW peak-load. The level of variability at a 0.5-min compared to a 30-min time resolution was significant as the peak power increased more than 270%. Using coarser temporal granularity ranging from 0.5 to 30-min substantially affected the PDF shape for the PVG and HCL. The shape was skewed more frequently near those hours with lower power, something that removed many of the extremes. The extreme ends of the PDF were of potential interest as they represented periods of very low or very high consumption/generation.

Since Spain has a liberalized electricity market, some electricity marketers now offer real-time pricing tariffs [17,23]. Thus, the electricity price model used a 1-hour discretized time resolution and computed the price from the day-ahead wholesale market of electricity [17] with a 10% benefit added for the electricity marketer plus the access toll of the current Spanish tariff 2.0 [102] plus taxes.

Regarding economic FCR data, it was assumed that the prosumer was a price-taker in the European FCR market (joint tender of German, Dutch, Belgian, Swiss, French, and Austrian SOs) [17,103]. This market consists of two main elements; payments for availability and utilization as well as payments for downward or upward regulation.

To assess the FCR power of a PV household-prosumer, hourly data of the upward and downward FCR power availability factor at the country level (in Spain) were used [17]. Moreover, for modelling the different cumulated FCR energies in Section 2.1, we considered the frequency data which the PDF for 2019 shows in Fig. 5. These data were provided by the Spanish SO at a specific point in the synchronous area of continental Europe (Hernani, Spain) [17].

As can be observed, high-frequency components were quite damped due to the effect of the system inertia and FCR provision. Some distinct peaks were visible in the medium range, which were mainly

because of the way the market was operated. Furthermore, Fig. 4c1 shows the cumulated stored FCR energy for one day in September, and Fig. 4c2 reflects the corresponding annual PDF. As granularity decreased, there was also increasingly less probability that the prosumer would be requested to ramp down power capacity to 0.5 kW.

Fig. 4. Input data for different time discretizations: (a) PVG of an MPVU; (b) HCL; (c) cumulated stored FCR energy for an MFCRU. (-1) profile for one representative day in September; (-2) annual PDF.

Fig. 5. PDF of the frequency signal at Hernani, Spain.

7. Results

Based on the formulation in Section 5, the overall system in Fig. 1, was modelled in the MATLAB programming environment to solve the optimization problem. The results obtained are presented in this section. This environment worked in a grid computation system which included 680 cores, 2 TB RAM, 6.2 TFlops of computing power, 13 TB of storage, and 32 calculation nodes with DDR at 20Gbit/s with a Sun Grid.

Given this framework, interesting conclusions were obtained regarding the granularity of data when PV household-prosumers deal with different scenarios of service complementarity. The performance of the optimization algorithm was firstly compared for different data granularity. After that, the accuracy and convergence of the proposed optimization algorithm was subsequently compared with other well-known algorithms. The next step was to focus on the best sizing results. The optimal results for the SFCPMS and FCREMS on the HESS were then added. Finally, the battery aging in different scenarios and data granularity were compared.

The simulations considered a time horizon of one year (ten days in each month) and seven resolutions for the granularity of data, from a half-minute to 30 minutes. This time horizon allowed for the daily, weekly, and annual cyclicity of PPD and PED profiles to be accurately assessed. The referential technical values and factors assumed for the cost model are summarized in Table 1. The parameters of the frequency control module for FCR provision came from [9,10]. The battery aging parameters are given in [17,103].¹⁰⁴¹⁰⁵¹⁰⁶¹⁰⁷¹⁰⁸

Table 1. Technical and financial parameters applied in the optimization.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
$C_{ad}(ddb)\{dds\}$ –Power specific capital cost for the AC/DC converter (battery converter) [SC converter]–	100 €/kW [4,33,99]	N_i $i \in \{bt, sc\}$ –ith minimum unit lifetime–	20 years	T –Income tax rate–	0% [17]
C_{bt} –Energy specific capital cost for the battery–	300 €/kWh [4,6,15,16,99,104]	P_{ad}^* (P_{ddb}), [P_{dds}] –Rated power of the minimum unit of AC/DC converter (DC/DC battery converter) [DC/DC SC converter]–	1 kW/unit	Δ_t –Discretization time-step–	30, 20, 10, 5, 2.5, 1, and 0.5-min
C_{pv} –Power specific capital cost for PV–	1000 €/kWp [4,99]	P_{bt+}^{\max} ($= -P_{bt-}^{\max}$) –Maximum discharge(charge) power for the minimum battery unit–	C-rate =1	χ_{bt}^{rat} –Rated DOD of the minimum battery unit–	80%
C_{sc} –Energy specific capital cost for the SC–	10000 €/kWh [4,104]	P_c –Contracted power from the electric mains–	5 kW	χ_{sc}^{rat} –Rated DOD of the minimum SC unit–	100%
d –Nominal discount rate–	3.5% [104]	P_{fcr} –Prequalified power capacity of the minimum FCR unit–	0.5 kW/unit	Ω_{bt}^{\max} –Maximum number of battery units installed–	25 units
g –Expected annual inflation –	1.4% [105]	P_{pv} –Rated power of the minimum PV unit–	1 kW/unit	Ω_{fcr}^{\max} –Maximum number of FCR units installed–	1 unit
LE_{bt}^{\max} –Maximum energy of the minimum battery unit–	1 kWh	$i_{O\&M}^i$ $i \in \{pv, bt, sc, ad, ddb, dds\}$ –Annual escalation rate of the operation and maintenance cost of the ith minimum unit–	1.4%, 2%, 0.3%, 0.3%, 0.3% [99,106]	Ω_{pv}^{\max} –Maximum number of FCR units installed–	20 units
LE_{sc}^{\max} –Maximum energy of the minimum SC unit–	0.1 kWh	r_{pv} –PV degradation rate–	0.5% [107,108]	Ω_{sc}^{\max} –Maximum number of SC units installed–	100 units
N_i $i \in \{pv, ad, ddb, dds\}$ –ith minimum unit lifetime–	25 years [4]	t –Time interval–	10^{-3} -s		

7.1. Performance comparison of the optimization algorithm

The optimal solution found by the algorithm proposed did not yield exactly the same result each time it was run. In order not to confuse differences in solutions stemming from data granularity with differences in solutions due to the nature of the algorithm, each calculation was repeated 30 times. The performance comparison of the algorithm was validated on the PV household-prosumer with HCL, PVG, HESS, and FCR (hereafter defined as scenario #4A). Fig. 6 shows the LCOE results. Also shown are the normalized computation times.

When data was defined on a finer granularity, the algorithm converged to the optimal fitness value after lower iterations. The higher the population size was, the lower the LCOE. This outcome was more significant for coarser data granularity. Nonetheless, as the population size got higher, the reduction in LCOE became smaller, which was possibly because a higher number of constraints had to be satisfied. The finer data model imposed additional security and dispatch requirements on the prosumer at each sub-period. As reflected in the standard deviation, the ranges of near optimal solutions decreased when higher resolution data were used. This indicated that many solutions gave approximately the same objective function, which became flatter around the optimum.

Computational cost was also an important issue, as shown in Fig. 6. The computational time was normalized by the reported time for a 30-min granularity and a population of 1000, which was 31 min 12 s on average. As can be observed, the computational load rapidly (and critically) increased with each increase of time resolution.

The size of sub-30-min models nonlinearly increased the difficulty of solving the resulting optimization problem. If the search space granularity was reduced, an exhaustive search converged proportionally faster, but at the expense of a less accurate approximation of the true solution. The rise in computational time was most noticeable for scenario #4A, as compared to the others (see Section 7.3). This was because the model had more complex constraints with respect to time when storage, FCR and SCF were included.

Fig. 6. Best solution for various population-size values and time granularity.

7.2. Accuracy and convergence comparison of the proposed optimization algorithm

To further demonstrate and compare the performance of the hybrid meta-heuristic optimization algorithm proposed, this section also provides the convergence characteristics of other well-known population-based heuristic algorithms such as PSO and GA. The comparison of the accuracy and convergence was proved in scenario #4A, as stated in previous section. Furthermore, the reference case to be compared focused on the 30-min time granularity, and the proposed optimization algorithm used 500 iterations and a population size of 4000. Maintaining the same computational effort for all algorithms, each optimization was run 30 times again and resulted in the expected values and standard deviations in Fig. 7.

The PSO-based optimization algorithm obtained the fastest convergence, whereas the GA-based optimization had an intermediary convergence, as observed from the iterative LCOE values. The proposed hybrid meta-heuristic optimization algorithm based on WTTLBO yielded a smoother and more stable convergence compared with the PSO and GA. The WTTLBO-based optimization was found to be more robust and efficient since it produced the best LCOE value in the final stage. Although the PSO and GA were able to converge to obtain solutions of equal quality, it was necessary to increase the particle number and/or iterations. Thus, they had a higher computational cost.

Fig. 7. Comparison of best LCOE results by using different heuristic optimization algorithms, scenario #4A.

7.3. Time-step resolution influence on best sizing results

The influence of the granularity of data on the best solutions of the component sizing and its financial profitability is analyzed in this section. We thus deal with inputs under seven time-step resolutions when applying the integrated optimization in Section 5 to the PV household-prosumer in different scenarios of service complementary such as the following:

- Scenario #0A: scenario with HCL
- Scenario #0B: scenario with HCL and EVCL
- Scenario #1A: scenario with HCL and PVG (PV SFC enhancement)
- Scenario #2A: scenario with HCL, PVG, and HESS (PV SFC enhancement). SFCPMS is scheduled on HESS
- Scenario #2B: scenario #2A plus EVCL
- Scenario #3: scenario with an HESS and FCR (FCR provision). FCREMS is scheduled on HESS
- Scenario #4A: scenario with HCL, PVG, HESS, and FCR (PV SFC enhancement plus FCR provision). SFCPMS and FCREMS are scheduled on HESS
- Scenario #4B: scenario #4A plus EVCL

Economic and component sizing results for the whole planned scenarios and granularity of data are shown in Figs. 8 and 9. As reflected in scenario #1A, the optimization algorithm calculated the minimal cost configuration and forced the PVG to balance with HLC. The coarser the temporal resolution in the PPD profile was, the larger the PV sizing was. The underlying principle is fairly straightforward. By using a coarser resolution, the averaging effect on inputs (smoothing of peaks and troughs of demand and production) causes the proportion of exported power to the grid to be underestimated (less relevant for imported power). This means that the matching capability is overestimated.

For the 30-min time granularity, the best PV sizing was about 42.1% higher than that resulting from the use of 0.5-min profiles. However, the NPV slightly increased by 2.6% as the granularity became finer. The decrease in PV sizing did not lead to a substantially higher NPV.

By exploring scenario #3, averaging PED time series over longer time periods involved a higher PED, and therefore required larger HESS sizing. In fact, when data were defined at the finest granularity, the resulting optimal battery and SC sizing decreased by 37.6% and 92.5%, respectively. A finer time resolution was crucial for the lower amount of reserves scheduled for the intra-step variations. The finer the interval resolution was, the greater the reduction in the investment cost, and the lower the NPV, up to 354.7%. This highlights the importance of low time resolutions, especially when dealing with single FCR provision.

The availability of storage had an impact on the conclusions with respect to data granularity since this provided an alternate means for balancing the smoothing of demand and production fluctuations. In scenario #2A, the battery allowed more PVG to be used to meet the HLC. Accordingly, the optimal PV sizing levels were indeed somewhat higher than in scenario #1A. The influence of the finest granularity decreased PV sizing by 22.9% and increased the NPV by only 0.6%. In the case of HESS sizing, this effect was even more noticeable since the battery and SC sizing dropped by about 23.4% and 464.2%, respectively. Because averaging affected the input profiles, it also influenced the total energy required

(i.e., the HESS sizing). Minimum values of battery sizing and NPV were found at about 10-min time intervals. Nonetheless, the AC/DC converter, as compared to the battery and SC converters, was less power-efficient at this mid-range time interval.

In scenario #2B, larger demands, due to EVCL which behaved stably, reduced and reversed the difference in the PV and battery sizing change with increasing time resolutions. Battery sizing increased more than PV sizing. So there was a shift from the unpredictable PV supply source, which may lead to large intermittent and fluctuating spikes in importing and exporting power, to the more stable source of generation, the battery. The worsening in the NPV due to the fine-grained solutions was about 2.8% with a minimum value around 10-min time intervals.

Above best sizing results were a first indication that the influence of granularity depended heavily on the complementary scenario setup and constraints used. This stemmed from the difference of the averaging effect on each PPD. In this regard, when scenario #4A was compared to #2A, the additional FCR provision in #4A substantially changed the behavior in PV, battery, and SC sizing when the finest data granularity was avoided (i.e., 1 and 0.5-min). Results for shorter temporal intervals were strikingly different from those for longer temporal intervals because cumulated FCR energy behaved differently at this finer granularity (Fig. 4c2). Furthermore, the NPV for #4A increased up to 8.3%. In contrast, the comparison of scenarios #2B and #4B reflected a lesser impact of FCR on the granularity influence, except for battery sizing and NPV. Even though the 3.7% increase in NPV was a slightly lower than in the case without FCR, it was still substantial. Again, the higher and more stable EVCL could be the reason for this.

Even though the pattern in the change of best component sizing was dissimilar with data resolution change, the bias in battery cycling lifetime was evidently much smaller except for scenario #3.

Taking into account the increased amount of data while maintaining computational tractability, there is no need to use data at the finest granularity, as the NPV increase was very small, and the change in sizing was limited to using 0.5- minute data rather than 5-min data.

Fig. 8. Summary of the best component sizing results and cost composition breakdown, scenarios #0, #1A, and #3.

Fig. 9. Summary of best component sizing results and cost composition breakdown, scenarios #2 and #4.

7.4. Optimal SFCPMS and FCREMS

This section presents a comparative temporal analysis of the influence that data granularity has on the optimal SFCPMS (Figs. 10 to 12, Figs. 14 and 15) and on the optimal FCREMS (Figs. 13 and 14). The figures show thus three samples of data granularity for the first two days in September.

The SFCPMS figures include the optimal power reference for the battery and SC ($p_{br,k}, p_{sc,k}$) along with the initial power references, namely, the achieved approximation and detail powers of the PPD profile after WT decomposition ($p_{app,k}, p_{det,k}$).

As can be observed in scenario #2A and 30-min data granularity, the approximation part of the PPD signal was transient-free, whereas the detail part occurred at the high-frequency part of the signal. The peak discharging power of the approximation part decreased from 2.68 to 2.40 kW (time 0.62), while charging power was reduced from 4.59 to 1.79 kW (time 1.85). This is an excellent effect of peak shaving on battery power. The detail part, which would be the SC power if the SFCPMS was not modelled, assisted the battery with a peak power of 1.33 kW (time 0.50), and captured a charging power of 2.79 kW (time 1.85).

The performance of the SFCPMS showed that it could maintain the SOCs in the HESS between the minimum and maximum values. Furthermore, the SFCPMS shifted the power burden on the battery to the SC to relieve the battery stress when the high PPD arrived. More specifically, this intelligent power splitting could be observed in the time interval of 0.66 to 0.70. During this period, the PPD became heavier and reached peak at around a time of 0.69. Meantime, the SFCPMS gave priority to assisting the battery rather than to tracking the SC SOC, and generated negative power to discharge the SC more. Additionally, the peak battery discharging power was further reduced to 1.12 kW (time 0), while SC peak discharging and charging powers were increased to 2.22 (time 0.69) and 1.35 kW (time 1.93), respectively. Overall, the SC, as a primary power source, successfully supplied and absorbed short-duration and peak power, and varied most rapidly among the three power sources. As reflected in the intermittency of battery cycles, the battery acted as a secondary power source and followed the daily macro cycles of the PPD profile. When the battery SOC was close to the minimum SOC value, this forced the AC grid to start working to ensure that the battery SOC did not further drop. The change in the SC SOC was an indicator of its higher utilization. As a result, the HESS operated timely and effectively, and the battery degradation was thus greatly reduced.

Based on the three snapshots of data granularity, when the interval resolution was more fine-grained, the outliers in the approximation part could strongly influence the battery results, and large biases in grid power could be expected. Nonetheless, the SFCPMS performed suitably as the attenuation in the battery power signal in relation to the approximation part increased when data resolution was finer. Nonetheless, the lowest SC sizing at the highest resolution led to the lowest SC support of the battery as the SC barely had any power and largely moved away from the detail part. Meanwhile the battery power and SOC showed the most fluctuations. Not surprisingly, the finer the resolution in the input series was, the more frequently the PV power crossed the HCL spikes and matching capability was overestimated (Fig. 8).

Fig. 10. Results for the optimal SFCPMS at scenario #1A for three samples of data granularity.

Fig. 11. Results for the optimal SFCPMS at scenario #2A for three samples of data granularity.

Fig. 12. Results for the optimal SFCPMS at scenario #2B for three samples of data granularity.

Fig. 13 shows the optimal results for the FCREMS from the PED profiles ($e_{ped-,k} = e_{fcr-,k}$ and $e_{ped+,k} = e_{fcr+,k}$) in scenario #3. This includes the optimal upward and downward FCR energy references for SC ($e_{sc+,k}, e_{sc-,k}$) along with the initial energy references, namely, the achieved upward and downward detail energies of the PED profiles after WT decomposition ($e_{det+,k}, e_{det-,k}$). As reflected in the 30-min data granularity, note that detail energy for SC assisted battery with a downward energy peak of 0.022

kWh versus 0.032 kWh of cumulated stored FCR energy (time 1.77). There was also a delivered upward energy peak of 0.064 kWh versus 0.095 kWh of cumulated released FCR energy (time 1.83).

The FCREMS not only controlled the SOCs in the HESS, but also shifted the energy burden on the battery to the SC. This smart energy splitting was observed around the time of 1.83 where the upward PED reached the peak and the FCREMS gave priority to assisting the battery rather than to tracking SC SOC, thus generating negative power to discharge the SC.

In practical terms, the FCR energy references for SC were the control variables to be determined. Thus, SC supplied or absorbed the peak FCR energy regulation. Its SOC thus fluctuated over a wide range. The battery followed a slow and fairly stable energy reference from the upcoming upward regulation throughout these days, and thus, the battery SOC decreased at a relatively low rate.

Regarding the three snapshots of data granularity, the finer the interval resolution, the closer the outliers in the optimal FCR energy references for SC, came the detail part. Large biases in battery energy were thus observed.

Fig. 13. Results for the optimal FCREMS at scenario #3 for three samples of data granularity.

The comparison of the SFCPMS results in scenarios #2A,B (Figs. 11 and 12) and #4A,B (Fig. 13a and 15) indicated that although scenario #2B or #4B included two loads (EVCL and HCL) in comparison to #2A or #4A, respectively, the speed of changes in EVCL was relatively low. As a result, the WT power splitting algorithm generated detail power references that were equivalent to the SC. Generally, there was a minor difference in the resulting battery SOC from the additional FCR provision in relation to scenarios #2A,B. This means that shallow cycling from the FCR provision had almost no effect on the macro cycles, and thus on the battery SOC. However, this FCR provision had more influence on the SC. The SC operated less often and therefore its SOC underwent lower changes in scenario #4 because of a more continuous and lower power requirement and a larger SC sizing. Moreover, in scenario #4, the optimal power reference for the battery moved closer to the approximation part, and the grid thus operated less often. A closer examination of the approximation part in scenarios #2A,B showed that they

were different from scenarios #4A,B, because of their different PPD profiles mainly during nocturnal hours. The reason for this was the EVCL.

The comparison of the FCREMS results in scenario #3 (Fig. 13) and #4A (Fig. 14) disclosed that a greater burden was supported by the SC in #4A. This can be explained by its higher optimal sizing. The battery barely absorbed and delivered power at the coarser temporal resolution.

Fig. 14. Results for the optimal SFCPMS (a) and FCREMS (b) at scenario #4A for three samples of data granularity.

Fig. 15. Results for the optimal SFCPMS at scenario #4B for three samples of data granularity.

7.5. Analysis of battery capacity degradation.

This section studies the influence of data granularity on the battery capacity degradation by using the degradation model in Section 2.4.1 that considered the DOD and C-rate. Fig. 16 depicts the statistical distributions for the C-rate and DOD over a year for all planned service scenarios and three samples of data granularity. These distributions reflected how the SFCPMS and FCREMS controlled the battery cycling.

Insofar as the 30-min data granularity in scenario #3, the C-rate showed a distinctly high peak at zero and a wide peak around -0.149 pu, whose range was up to -0.876 and 1.303 pu. The larger battery sizing in scenarios #2B and #4B as compared to #2A and #4A, respectively, resulted in C-rate distributions with peaks at lower levels. Scenario #2A had a distinct peak at 0.002 pu and a narrow and low peak at around -0.027 pu. In contrast, scenario #2B had a higher peak at around zero, but the main distribution was in the narrower interval of -0.15–0.206 pu.

This difference of distributions could be explained by the more stable PPD in scenario #2B. Concerning the DOD at each cycle, typical behavior from the PV SFC (scenarios #2 and #4) was observed with large DODs (e.g. daily cycling). However, scenario #3 resulted mostly in lower DODs, typically below 8.25% because battery power underwent significantly higher polarity reversals. The larger PPD in scenario #2B versus #2A increased the DOD values.

In the three snapshots of data granularity, the C-rate had a dissimilar range and average peak-to-mean ratio. However, the DOD demonstrated a much higher ‘peak-to-mean’ ratio. More specifically, the finer interval resolution was, the outliers in the C-rate usually slowly decreased, and the distribution tended to gradually approach a Gaussian distribution, except for scenario #4B. In contrast, the finer resolution led to a strong decrease in the DOD.

Fig. 16. Distributions for C-rate and cycle DOD throughout a year.

For most planned scenarios, the algorithm proposed optimally sized the battery so as to adjust its expected lifetime to about 20 years, which avoided the replacement cost. This resulted in a diverse

battery sizing for different PPD and PED profiles but in the same battery capacity degradation. In order to solely highlight the influence of the DOD at each cycle and the C-rate variables on battery capacity degradation for each scenario with a specific battery sizing, the battery capacity degradation was normalized by a ratio, the discharging energy cycled versus the battery capacity.

Fig. 17 thus displays this normalized capacity degradation and the DOD at each cycle during a 9-day snapshot. The multiplicity of depth cycles was due to the SFCPMS and FCREMS. As can be observed, when the interval resolution was finer, the normalized battery capacity degradation worsened. In this regard, the normalized degradation increase from largest to smallest was: 429% (#3), 6.34% (#2B), 5.34% (#2A), 0.47% (#4B), 0.27% (#4A).

Fig. 17. Profile of normalized battery capacity degradation and cycle DOD.

8. Conclusions

Increasing interest in services such as FCR and PV SFC for household-prosumers may in the near future significantly change domestic PPD and PED profiles. To understand the impact of such services, it is necessary to fully appreciate the sizing and management aspects of such prosumers. This type of holistic optimization treatment is necessary to fully capture the effects of coincidence in various service demands within and across dwellings.

To that end, this paper has presented and discussed high-resolution power and energy models as well as a hybrid meta-heuristic optimization algorithm based on WTTLBO that dealt with management strategies and sizing in a four-dimensional optimization problem. The design of the algorithm was flexibly adapted in terms of number of discrete states to suit the input profiles as defined on different time discretization levels. The proposed optimization algorithm was illustrated in MATLAB by means of the case study of PV household-prosumers in Spain that provided examples of different data granularity. Additionally, real data from FCR and energy market were used.

The influence of data granularity on the best solutions for sizing and its financial profitability was first discussed. Initially, for finer data granularity, the optimization results indicated that there was a cost increase ranging from 0.6% to 354.7%. There was also a drop or rise in optimal sizing levels of -42.1% to 28.2% for PV; -60.2% to 28.9% for the battery; and -4642.5% to -463.6% for the SC, depending on the service scenarios. Nonetheless, excluding scenario #3, the increase in costs did not exceed 8.3%.

Without storage (scenario #1A), optimal PV sizing noticeably fell to 42.1% when time resolutions were increased. The availability of storage had an impact on the results with respect to the data granularity since the smoothing of the demand and production fluctuations could take place by means of storage. Thus, in scenario #2A, PV sizing behaved similarly to the no-storage solution, whereas optimal HESS sizing largely decreased, particularly the SC. However, in scenario #2B, the larger PPD reduced and reversed the difference in the PV and battery sizing change with increasing time resolutions. On the other hand, the additional FCR provision did not substantially change the behavior in the PV, battery and SC sizing except for the finest data granularity. Therefore, there are no specific guidelines with respect to the influence the data granularity on sizing.

The results suggest that for profitability purposes, it is not necessary to use the finest data granularity except for scenarios #3 and #4A. In fact, the high-resolution data showed that many solutions had a similar outcome, such that even near-optimal solutions were able to produce satisfactory outcomes. However, when evaluating the sizing rather than the NPV, accuracy can be gained by using the finest resolution data.

Furthermore, when the objective is not to optimize average prosumer performance (cost effectiveness) but rather to increase component performance (e.g. battery aging), the short-term fluctuations should be suitably represented in the optimization process. In any case, when 0.5-min data rather than 5-min data were used, the NPV increase was very small and the change in sizing was somewhat limited. Consequently, considering the computational burden and limits to modelling flexibility that accompany the use of high-resolution data, it is not advisable to use data with time-steps smaller than five minutes for optimization purposes. This provides a sizing close to that of the finest resolution.

The results obtained in several service scenarios highlighted that the combination of FCR and SFC was clearly complementary. Furthermore, the incomes and savings obtained, thanks to the incorporation of PV, HESS, and FCR provision were higher than the amortization costs.

The optimal results for the SFCPMS and FCREMS showed that the SC successfully supplied and absorbed short-duration and peak power from the PPD for the PV SFC, as well as the corresponding short-duration and peak energy from the PED for the FCR. The battery followed the fairly stable power of the daily macro cycles of the PPD together with the slow change of the PED required by FCR energy regulation. The AC grid started to work only under high and continuous PPD conditions.

Regarding data granularity, it can be concluded that when interval resolution was finer, the biases in battery were larger. As a result, battery degradation was significantly increased per normalized kWh

delivered up to 6.34% for finer data granularity (excluding scenario #3). Battery aging thus played a crucial role in prosumer profitability because of the replacement cost.

The fact that the data sample was from a single PV household-prosumer in Spain is a limitation of this study. However, this data sample was sufficient to achieve our primary objective, which was to demonstrate the usefulness of this optimization methodology and to examine the impact that temporal granularity and complementarity of services can have on the optimal results. In conclusion, hopefully, this study will lead to future work and discussion in the research community regarding the provision of complementary services by residential PV prosumers and encourage similar work on datasets from other multi-family residential buildings.

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